

«SINGING WITH THE HEART» PURITANS MUSIC IN NEW ENGLAND

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Abstract

The Puritans were English Protestants dissatisfied with the limited extent of the English Reformation. Before Puritans migrated to New England, they hoped to change the Anglican Church to make it more «pure» by adhering to the doctrines of the French theologian Jean Calvin whose doctrine Puritans had embraced during their Marian exile. Puritans settled by waves in New England in 1630s and establish a colony under an official charter from the King of England. They ruled the Massachusetts Bay Colony until 1684. The objective of this paper is to show that music was not «silenced» during the Puritans colonization period. Actually, Puritans reserved a very important role to the music in singing Psalms which represented for them an individual experience to improve the quality of their souls, searching for signs of God's favor. Moreover, musical instruments were used for domestic purposes and this practice was also encouraged by puritan clergy. Also composing new tunes was allowed. The fervor in searching signals of a true spiritual experience may have, in the long term, induced people to introduce individual variations and embellishments to the melodies which created many challenges in psalmody congregational performance. Towards the end of the sixteenth century this challenge led to a serious discussion which resulted in singing *by note* the melodies. Like other European missionaries, Puritans used the music, namely singing Psalm in local Massachusetts dialect on English tunes, to boost the conversions of the American Indians. However, the Indian psalmody sounded different in terms of stylistic conventions, timbre, syllabication of the lyrics and resulted, according to the words of one the Puritan Governors «a Psalme sung in the Indian tongue, and Indian meeter». Due to King Philip's War, which began in 1675, the conversion process which Puritans have started ended.

INTRODUCTION

For many people, Puritan society reminds images of ships landing in the New World, men and women in dark clothes or bigot worshippers. As ironically noted: «neither students nor professional historians are likely to use images or conjure up images associated with Puritans playing musical instruments, singing, or crowding into theaters».¹

Puritans settled by waves in New England in 1630s. Unlike the Pilgrims, which had separated from the Church of England, Puritans had an official charter from the King of England to establish a colony. They ruled the Massachusetts Bay Colony until 1684 when the early liberties granted them by the Crown were rescinded. In the same year, the Bay Colony became a royal province with a royally appointed governor and with the Church of England as the official church.

¹ DANIELS 1973, p. 51.

It took about one century since Puritan's arrival in New England before the first advertisement of a «Concert of Musick on Sundry Instruments» in the North American colonies appeared on February 3rd, 1729 in the *Boston Gazette*.² This event took place a few years after the installation in the King's Chapel in Boston of a small organ (four stops), *The Brattle organ* (1713), and the call of «a sober person to play skillfully on the organs (*sic*) with a loud noise».³

Due to the long period of time during which secular music apparently disappeared in the Massachusetts Bay Colony, a number of scholars came to the conclusions that Puritans were simply music-hating people. For example Covey, considering the Puritans a specific group of Calvinists, concluded that:

In general everywhere in Europe and America during the colonial period, Calvinism was lethal to music, secular and sacred, in direct proportion to its independence of other influences.⁴

The objective of this paper is to show that music was not «silenced» in New England during early colonization period. On the contrary, so long the music was confined in the meetinghouses or at home, there was a quite intense musical life. Also the local puritan intellectual community, which was in strict contact with England theologians, discussed intensively about significance and nature of music.⁵ Furthermore, the use of musical instruments at home and even musical composition were encouraged by puritan clergy, provided that the accompaniment and the invented tunes were used to have a meaningful and heartfelt experience. Again, Puritans used the music as a «tool» to boost the conversion of the American Indians in the *Praying towns* that were founded in New England but the King Philip's War interrupted the conversion process which Puritans started.

PURITANS AND CALVINISTS

The Puritans were English Protestants dissatisfied with the limited extent of the English Reformation. Before Puritans migrated to New England, they hoped to change the Anglican Church

² LAMBERT 1996, p. 409.

³ MILLIGAN, 1934, p. 228.

⁴ COVEY 1951, p. 388. Actually, in the paper Covey seriously questioned the statements of another scholar, Scholes [SCHOLES 1933], who re-evaluated Puritan music in the 1930's.

⁵ Music was also part of the Liberal Art education program at Harvard College. Cfr. BEVERIDGE 1979.

to make it more «pure» by adhering to the doctrines of the French theologian Jean Calvin whose doctrine Puritans had embraced during their Marian exile (1553-1558).⁶

As far as music is concerned, Calvinists rejected the complexity of plain chant or polyphony which were not in line with the needs and capacities of an ordinary congregation. The refusal of this kind of music built Calvin's false reputation as an «enemy» of the music as a whole. On the contrary, Calvin regarded music as one of the most precious gifts of God to mankind:

Or entre les... choses, qui sont propres pour recreer l'homme et luy donner volupté, la Musicque est ou la premiere, ou l'une des principales: et nous faut estimer que c'est un don de Dieu deputed à c'est usage.⁷

Calvin's main concern was avoiding in music any deviations from the message of the Bible and this led him to censure the secular music which he considered to instill sensual temptations:

Seulement que le monde soit si bien advisé, qu'au lieu de chansons en partie vaines & frivoles, en partie sottes & lourdes, en partie sales & vilaines, et par conséquent mauvais & nuisibles, dont il a usé par ci devant, il se accoustume ci après à chanter ces divins & celestes Cantiques avec le bon Roy David.⁸

Accordingly, he restricted his musical texts to the translations of Psalms in French, collected in the *Genevan Psalter* (1539) and promoted the singing of Psalms in unison, without instrumental accompaniment. In his mind this assured that the music did not distract the worshipper from the message of the words. The ban of musical instruments, apart from the desire for moderation, appears also as a logical consequence of the demand for intelligence and the importance of the text, especially if it is considered that the role of the instruments in the Catholic service was not merely that of accompanying the singers.⁹ It should be noted that Calvin expressly stated that he did not

⁶ «We do not go to New-England as separatists from the Church of England though we cannot but separate from the corruptions in it», Francis Higginson. Cfr. MORRIS 2007, p. 124.

⁷ Comm. in Genesin - CAL. XXIII, 100. CFR. CLIVE 1957, p 81.

⁸ *Joannis Calvinii opera quae supersunt omnia*, vol. II, p. 21. Cfr. BERTOLINI 2012.

⁹ The banning of all instruments from the service made it, however, necessary for Calvin to furnish an explanation for the frequent allusions to them in the Old Testament, for instance in the books of the Prophets and the psalms themselves which make it clear that these instruments were widely used. Calvin's explanation is that Jews were - at that time - still in a state of religious infancy. Cfr. CLIVE 1957, p. 92.

condemn musical instruments in themselves and admitted the instruments, subject to certain restrictions: they were allowed, but only *outside* the church.¹⁰

When Marian exiles came back to England in 1558 (when Elisabeth I's reign started), they fiercely contrasted the «Cathedral music», i.e. the music of the Church of England, which they believed too close to Catholic liturgy.¹¹ For their service music, Puritans compiled other editions of the *Genevan Psalter*, which was at the end superseded by *The Whole Book of Psalms*, often referred to as *Sternhold and Hopkins Psalter* (1562). The music of this psalter was not a product of English tradition, but it was strongly influenced by *Genevan Psalter* and Elizabethan congregations did not take too many of these tunes.¹² It is worth noticing that singing Psalms became also part of musical life on ships departing to America and it was a custom on English ships to sing a psalm at the changing of the watch.¹³

SINGING PSALMS

After the settlement of the Massachusetts Bay Colony, a committee of 30 New England clergymen, – «more distinguished for their piety and learning than for their poetic gifts»¹⁴ – replaced the old psalters with a publication based on a new metrical translation of the Psalms, *The Whole Book of Psalms Faithfully Translated into English Meter*, henceforth referred to as *The Bay Psalm Book*. This was the first book to be printed in New England in 1640. The authors were able to study texts of previous Psalters, the *Geneva Bible*, and the *Bible* in Hebrew to determine the best translation of every phrase rather than paraphrasing the psalms from the *Geneva Bible* as previous versions had.¹⁵ The psalms were intended to be sung by everyone and

¹⁰ «Au reste il est vray... que la fleute et le tabourin, et choses semblables de leur nature ne sont point a condamner: c'est seule ment l'abus des hommes: mais le plus souvent on en pervertit le bon usage. Car il est certain que iamais le tabourin ne sonne pour faire resiouir les hommes, qu'il n'y ait de la vanité, ie ne di point superflue, mais comme brutale, car voila les hommes qui sont transportez, tellement qu'ils ne s'esgayent point d'une ioye moderee [...] (Sermon LXXIX sur le livre de Job, xxi - CAL. XXXIV, 226-7).» Cfr. CLIVE 1957, p. 93.

¹¹ GOODMAN 2012, p. 699.

¹² TEMPERLEY 2021, p. 5.

¹³ WOODFIELD 1995, p. 44.

¹⁴ LOWENS 1995, p. 24.

¹⁵ FARRER 2004, p. 9.

to join together in heart and voice to praise the Lord, for as David's psalms have been showed, were sung in heart and voice together by the twenty-four orders of the musicians of the temple.¹⁶

The worshipper was reminded that the use of the book is recommended

that so we may sing in Sion the Lord's songs of praise according to his own will, until he take us from hence, and wipe away all our tears, and bid us enter into our Master's joy to sing eternal hallelujahs.¹⁷

Actually, the *Bay Psalm book* did not contained music till the ninth edition which appeared in 1698. Apparently, the absence of the music was not an obstacle for singing, because Puritans used the «lining-out» practice: the pastor or a leader, often called the «precentor», led the singing by starting to sing each line ahead of the congregation. The congregation would then imitate, repeating the leader's lines as they heard them. Lining-out the psalm verses had also the advantage for musically illiterate worshippers to facilitate the singing without reading scores. Moreover, this practice reinforced the centrality of Scripture in Puritan worship because congregation members had to listen, internalize, and then repeat the lines.¹⁸ This was also consistent with Puritans (and Calvinists) goal of the direct acquisition of the scriptural Word by the worshipper rather than listening to *interpretation* of scriptural texts like in Catholic religion.¹⁹

Singing Psalms was for Puritans an exquisite individual experience to improve the quality of their souls, searching for signs of God's favor.²⁰ During the singing of the Psalms, they carefully monitored their emotions because they were essentially obsessed in finding any signals of a true spiritual experience.²¹ This is strictly connected with Calvin's theology: God had chosen a few people, «the elects», for salvation and the rest of humanity is condemned to eternal damnation but no one really knows if he or she is saved or damned. So, Puritans lived in a constant state of «spiritual anxiety», searching for signs of God's favor or anger. «Crying tears» and «singing with grace in your heart» (PAUL, *Colossian 3:16*) were signs of God's favor and a proof that the Spirit decided to inhabit the singer. It should be noted that considering the heart as the organ to feel a

¹⁶ «The Preface», *The Bay Psalm Book*, 1640.

¹⁷ *ibid.*

¹⁸ FARRER 2004, p. 8.

¹⁹ DELL'ANTONIO 2011, Ch. 1, p. 3.

²⁰ *ivi*, p. 694.

²¹ GOODMAN 2012, p. 691 describes an experience reported in the diary of Samuel Sewall, a puritan judge in Boston. During the singing of a psalm with a group of neighbors in the privacy of his home in August 1695, he could hardly sing at all. Instead, his voice choked and he started to cry.

religious rapture was echoed by contemporary Christian theology. For example, according to Johannes Saubert, a Nuremberg theologian:

It is the spirit of God that tunes up so the song can be continued, that is, that it goes through the heart... Hence it is not us who sing or speak spiritually in this way, but it is the spirit of our heavenly Father that lives in us.²²

Cotton and Shepard in *Singing of Psalms, a Gospel Ordinance* (1647), exhorted the worshippers to «make a melody in our hearts and voices», so that singing Psalms would not be reduced to a «lip-labour» and «lost labour».²³ Cotton Mather assured the members of the congregation that they could indeed experience a sort of ecstasy by «contemplating the words while singing them».²⁴ The same author writes:

In singing our spiritual songs, let us be inquisitive after those motions of piety which are discernible in the verse now before us; and let us with soul flying away to God, for them, try whether we cannot fly with them, and strive to come at the like, and give not over the struggle till we feel ourselves come into an holy symphony with the saints who had their hearts burning within them when they sang these things unto the Lord. . . . Yea, thou art already caught up to paradise in them.²⁵

This individualistic approach in singing Psalms and in searching any signs of God's favor, became so important for the Puritans to induce people to introduce personal variations and embellishments to the melodies in order to achieve the best spiritual experience in singing.²⁶ This could explain the challenges in psalmody congregational performance towards the end of the seventeenth century which lead to a serious discussion between those who desired to keep the «usual» or common method of lining-out, and those who wanted to replace it with «regular» singing (using musical notation and defined rules). Cotton Mather promoted «regular» psalm-singing. In a letter to Thomas Hollis, Jr., dated 1723, he mentioned the tensions between puritans worshippers:

²² SAUBERT, *Seelen Music* (1624), 10. Quoted in VARWIG 2023, p. 87. «der Geist Gottes ists / welcher anstimmt / damit das Gesang seinen fortgang habe / das ist / das es durch das Hertz gehe / Act. 2. Darumb wir sinds nicht / die wir also Geistlich singen oder reden / sondern der Geist unsers himlischen Vatters ists / der in uns wohnet.» Johannes Saubert, *Seelenmusik, wie dieselbe am Sontag Cantate ... gehört worden*, (Nuremberg: Halbmayr, 1624), 10.

²³ *The Singing of Psalmes, a Gospel Ordinance*, 2, 1647.

²⁴ Cfr. FARRER 2004, p. 7.

²⁵ Cotton Mather, *The Accomplished Singer* (Boston 1721), Harvard: Harvard College Library, *passim*. Quoted in BEVERIDGE 1979, p. 163.

²⁶ GOODMAN 2012, p. 716

A mighty spirit came lately upon abundance of our people to reform their singing, which was degenerated in our assemblies to an irregularity which made a jar in the ears of the more curious and skillful singers. Our ministers generally encouraged the people to accomplish themselves for a regular singing and a more beautiful psalmody. Such numbers of good people (and especially young people) became regular singers that they could carry it in the congregation. But,...who would believe it? Tho' in the more polite city of Boston this design met with a general acceptance, in the country, where they have more of the rustic, some numbers of elder and angry people bore zealous testimonies against these wicked innovations, and this bringing in of popery.... The paroxysms have risen to that height as to necessitate the convening of several ecclesiastical councils for the composing of the differences and animosities arisen on this occasion.²⁷

The usual way of singing Psalms ended in 1720s, when singing schools and publications introduced rules of music and methods for singing and encouraged the younger generation of Puritans to sing *by note* the melodies.

For Puritans the choice of the melodies to be used were strictly connected to the meaning of singing Psalms: this was not just a ceremonial duty, settled by men, but it was a moral duty, i.e. something pertaining to the soul's ultimate salvation (like for example baptism, prescribed directly by God). The most suitable melodies would have been the Hebrew original melodies which, unfortunately, have not survived. New England puritan writers, differently from other Protestants, including Luther, which selected pre-existing popular or catholic melodies, started a theological discussion on the best suitable melodies for singing Psalms.²⁸ At the end they agreed to welcome newly composed music, provided that this could incentivate the worshippers to have a meaningful and sincere spiritual experience. Music composition was also encouraged at individual level for private singing, as it is evident in the following passage of *Singing of Psalms* :

Wee grant also, that any private Christian, who hath a gift to frame a spirituall Song, may both frame it, and sing it privately, for his own private comfort, and remembrance of some spirituall benefit, or deliverance: . . .²⁹

Following Calvin prescriptions, Puritans considered instruments to be distracting in singing psalms at congregational level. Therefore, the psalms in meeting were always unaccompanied. However, the *Singing of Psalms* offered guidelines for the private use of instruments:

Singing with Instruments, was typicall, and so a ceremonial worship, and therefore is ceased. But Singing with heart and voyce is a morall worship. [...] Nor do we forbid the private use of an instrument of Musick therewith all; So that attention to the instrument, doe not divert the heart from the attention to the matter of the Song.³⁰

²⁷ SILVERMAN 1971, p. 376. Quoted in KUNKEL 1989, p. 25.

²⁸ GOODMAN 2012, p. 710.

²⁹ COTTON 1647, 2.

³⁰ COTTON 1647, 15.

Violins, fiddles, and the *kit*, a small violin, were available to the Puritans, while keyboard instruments were costly and difficult to ship from Europe in the seventeenth century, and the organ was considered «popish». Lambert performed a thorough investigation of the extant household inventories, filed between 1630 and 1730 and copied into record books upon the death of a household in Massachusetts Bay Colony.³¹ She identified a great number of musical instruments, including virginals, clavichords, lutes, guitars, citterns, *viola da gamba*, wind instruments, etc., taken by Puritans from Europe to America.

PURITAN AND AMERICAN INDIANS

Another important aspect of the Puritans early colonization life in America was their relationships with American Indians. Puritans considered Indians «uncivilized» pagans in particular danger of perdition unless they could be converted. According to Puritan rhetoric, while church members were shepherds, Indians were «wolves dressed in sheep's clothing». A more alarming theme among Puritans was the tendency to view Indians as actual wolves: a perfect way of dehumanizing them.³² Coleman reviewed the writings of missionaries in New England and observed that in their records «English men and women spoke and sang in tone of 'elation and joy', while Indians bellowed like animals» and one of the missionary asserted that Indians «act like wolves and are to be dealt withal as wolves».³³ Also Cotton Mather in *Decennium Luctuosum* or *The Sorrowful Decade* (1699), in which describes the violence of Indians during the King Philip's War, used the wolf image to depict the Indians: in the eulogy for a Puritan minister, Shubael Dummer, killed by Indians, writes:

Dummer The Shepard Sacrific'd
By Wolves, because the Sheep he prized.³⁴

American Indian music impressions can be found in the stories of Indian captivities, which became a new type of literature since the sixteenth century. This is how, for example, Ms. Mary Rowlandson describes an Indian ceremony in 1682:

³¹ LAMBERT 1996.

³² COLEMAN 2004, p. 41-43.

³³ *Ibidem*

³⁴ KENNEDY 2017, p. 233.

They being busie in dressing themselves, and getting ready for their Dance: which was carried on by eight of them; four men and four Squaws: [...]. All Dancers were after the same Manner. There were two there singing and knocking on a Kettle for their Musick. They kept hopping up and down one after another.³⁵

Another author expressed his astonishment at the Indians' attitude towards death:

They make little of death when it is inevitable, and despite all tortures which can be inflicted upon them while dying, manifesting no sorrow, usually singing on the occasion!³⁶

In his diary, John Winthrop, the Puritan leader, wrote: «The Indians sang themselves asleep with barbarous singing!».³⁷ Also John Eliot, the most important puritan missionary, did not appreciate the Indian way of singing:

Lamentation and Joy: of which kinde of sounds our Musick and Song is made. Ululation, Howling, Yelling, or Mourning: and of that kind of sound is their Music and Song made³⁸.

Like other Spanish and French missionaries, Puritans considered the music, namely lining-out Psalm in local Massachusetts dialect on English tunes, a «tool» to boost the conversions of the American Indians. Eliot translated the Bible and the Psalms into the local Massachusetts dialect (1663). However, since most of the Indians, were illiterate, the effect of these translations should not be overemphasized.³⁹ Eliot got also the idea to place Indians to be converted in separated «praying towns» where they could be sedentary and isolated from both settlers and other heathen Indians. By 1674 there were fourteen Praying towns with a total population of about 4000 American Indians.⁴⁰ This is similar to what Jesuits did in other parts of the America but there were also differences: Jesuits tried to adapt to native lifestyle, Puritans did not compromise from their standards. According to Puritans the conversion process had to start adopting an English lifestyle (by cutting hair, living in a house, wearing English-style clothes, embracing English gender norms, etc...⁴¹).

³⁵ Mary Rowlandson, *A Narrative of the Captivity*. Cfr. HOLLIS 1961, p. 102.

³⁶ *Ivi* p. 103.

³⁷ *Ivi* p. 104.

³⁸ GOODMAN 2012, p. 803. From these words the association of Indians with animals is evident.

³⁹ SALISBURY 1974, p. 43.

⁴⁰ KUNKEL 1989, p. 28.

⁴¹ Long hair was a distinction between Englishmen and Indians. In one of his sermons in Boston, Charles Chauncy noted that wearing long hair associated one with «Indians & pagans whose abominable customs the Lord hath forbidden his people to follow». Cfr. HOLLIS 1961, p. 101.

Despite the obstacles and length of the conversion process, missionaries could claim, in an initial phase of their activity, some successes. According to Governor John Endicott that visited a praying town:

There was a Psalme sung in the Indian tongue, and Indian meeter, to an English tune, and by one of themselves, that but the rest might follow, and he read it very distinctly without missing a word as we could judge, and the rest sang cheerfully, and pretty tuneable [...].⁴²

Actually, the Indian psalmody «sounded different»: Indians were unfamiliar with Western scales and rhythms. Moreover contrafacting English melodies was a problem because the new lyrics did not fit the old tunes which were stretched or squeezed to accommodate the Massachusetts dialect. Also stylistic conventions regarding vocal timbre were very different. These were most probably some of the reasons behind Endecott's statement that «there was a Psalme sung in the Indian tongue, and Indian meeter».⁴³

In 1675, the tensions between Indians and English colonists worsened and King Philip's War began, bringing a terrible destruction and many atrocities in New England. In this war there was an important episode mentioned by Goodman in his research on Indian Psalmody: a band of former Christian Indian converts attacked colonies who barricade in a building. Unexpectedly, Indians started to «sing a psalm [...] and made an hideous noise somewhat resembling singing».⁴⁴ It was the former Christians' singing purposefully disrupted, a symbolic act to despise the main means to express devotion to God for the Puritans: the Psalms. At the end of the war, in 1677, those Indians who had not been killed or sold as slaves were all concentrated in one praying town, a sort of reservation for an entire native population, reduced to a state of complete dependency on the Englishmen.

CONCLUSIONS

From the above findings, it can be concluded that the stereotypes of Puritans as music-hating people have to be rejected and music was not «silenced» in New England during early colonization period. This is in line with the most recent historiographical interpretations. Puritans reserved a very important role to the music in singing Psalms which represented for them an individual experience to improve the quality of their souls, searching for signs of God's favor. Moreover, musical

⁴² John Endicott, *Strenght out of Weakness*, 49. Quoted in KUNKEL 1989, p. 30.

⁴³ cfr. *supra*

⁴⁴ GOODMAN 2012, p. 818.

instruments were used for domestic purposes and this practice was also encouraged by puritan clergy. Composing new tunes was also allowed. The fervor in searching signals of a true spiritual experience may have, in the long term, induced people to introduce individual variations and embellishments to the melodies which created many challenges in psalmody congregational performance. Towards the end of the sixteenth century this challenge led to a serious discussion which resulted in the introduction of rules of music and methods for singing *by note* the melodies.

Lining-out the Psalms in local Massachusetts dialect on English tunes was considered an excellent way to nurture the spiritual development of the Native Indians. However, the Indian psalmody sounded different in terms of stylistic conventions, timbre, syllabication of the lyrics and resulted, according to the words of one the puritan Governors «a Psalme sung in the Indian tongue, and Indian meeter». Due to King Philip's War, which began in 1675, the conversion process which Puritans had started came to an end. In 1677 those Indians who had survived the war were concentrated in one praying town and reduced to a state of complete dependency on the Englishmen.

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